

Psychosocial Determinants and Investment Behavioural Dynamics Among Salaried Investors

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Abstract : Introduction Investment behaviour among salaried individuals in Tamil Nadu is shaped by a range of psychosocial determinants. This study explores how psychological factors such as risk tolerance, cognitive biases, and emotional responses interact with social influences like peer pressure, cultural norms, and socioeconomic status to influence investment decisions. Understanding these dynamics is crucial as they contribute to both optimal and suboptimal investment behaviours among salaried investors in urban areas. Methods The study employs a quantitative research design with a stratified simple random sampling technique. Primary data were collected from 576 participants, divided into individual and corporate investors, across Tamil Nadu's 38 districts. Data collection utilized a structured questionnaire, and analysis was performed using factor analysis, Z-tests, and regression analysis. Exploratory Factor Analysis identified four key factors affecting investment behaviour: Investor-Related Factors, Market/Environment-Related Factors, Investment Related Factors, and Company-Specific Characteristics. Results Factor analysis revealed that Investor-Related Factors, Market/Environment-Related Factors, Investment-Related Factors, and Company-Specific Characteristics account for significant variance in investment behaviour. The Z-tests indicated notable differences between individual and corporate investors in terms of these factors. Regression analysis showed that psychological determinants like cognitive biases and emotional responses significantly impact investment decisions. Conclusion The study highlights that psychosocial determinants play a crucial role in shaping the investment behaviour of salaried individuals in Tamil Nadu. Financial advisors and policymakers need to consider these factors to develop tailored strategies that address cognitive biases and enhance financial decision-making. Improved financial education and advisory services can help mitigate suboptimal investment behaviours and foster better financial outcomes. Originality This research provides a comprehensive analysis of the psychosocial factors influencing investment behaviour among salaried investors in Tamil Nadu. By integrating psychological and social determinants and employing robust statistical methods, the study offers new insights into the investment dynamics in a specific regional context. This contributes to the broader literature on Behavioural finance and informs better financial planning and advisory practices.

Keywords: Psychosocial Determinants, Investment Behaviour, Cognitive Biases, Risk Tolerance, Salaried Investors

Introduction

Investment behaviour, particularly among salaried investors, is profoundly shaped by a complex interplay of psychosocial determinants. In the major cities of Tamil Nadu, these determinants include psychological factors like risk tolerance Srinivasan & Nair, (2023), cognitive biases, and emotional responses, along with social factors such as peer influence, cultural norms, and socioeconomic status Subramanian & Sharma, (2023). Understanding these factors is essential for comprehending how salaried individuals make investment decisions Iyer & Subramanian, (2023) which often vary based on their psychological predispositions and social environments Choudhury, (2022); Rao & Saha, (2021). Psychologically, salaried investors are frequently influenced by risk aversion and cognitive biases such as overconfidence, loss aversion, and anchoring Srinivasan & Kumar, (2023). These biases can lead to suboptimal investment decisions, such as excessive caution or unwarranted risk-taking Subramani & Venkat, (2022). Emotional responses, especially fear and greed, also play a significant role, often leading to herd behaviour, where investors follow market trends without critical analysis Bhaskar & Natarajan, (2023).

Socially, factors such as peer influence and societal expectations shape the investment Behaviour of salaried individuals. In Tamil Nadu's urban context, investment decisions are often swayed by the advice and actions of peers and family members Krishnan & Varadarajan, (2022). Cultural norms around savings and investment, particularly the emphasis on property and gold, further guide investment choices Reddy & Murugan, (2021). Socioeconomic status also complicates the investment landscape. Salaried investors in higher income brackets tend to have more diversified portfolios, while those with lower incomes often prioritize safety Mohan & Arul, (2021) and liquidity Prasad & Shankar, (2022), favouring traditional investment avenues Jayakumar & Ravi, (2021). This divergence underscores the need for tailored financial education and advisory services that consider both psychological Das & Singh, (2021) and social factors Vijay & Manikandan, (2022).

Psychosocial Determinants and Investment Behavioural Dynamics

Investment behaviour among salaried investors is a multifaceted process influenced by a complex array of psychosocial determinants. In the context of Tamil Nadu's major cities, these determinants include psychological factors such as risk tolerance Choudhury, (2022), cognitive biases Iyer & Ramachandran, (2024), and emotional responses Pandey & Roy, (2024) as well as social influences like cultural norms, peer pressure, and social networks. Risk tolerance Mohan & Balakrishnan, (2022) a key psychological determinant, plays a pivotal role in shaping investment decisions. Investors with high risk tolerance are more likely to engage in aggressive investment strategies, while those with low risk tolerance may prefer safer, conservative options Gupta & Sharma, (2023). Cognitive biases, such as overconfidence and loss aversion, also significantly impact investment behaviour Viswanathan & Ramesh, (2023). Overconfident investors tend to overestimate their knowledge and abilities, leading to excessive trading and suboptimal returns Rao et al., (2022). Conversely, loss aversion drives investors to avoid losses rather than seek equivalent gains, often resulting in a reluctance to sell underperforming assets Patel & Reddy, (2021) Emotional responses, particularly fear and greed, further complicate decision-making processes, often leading to irrational investment choices driven by short-term

market fluctuations Kumar & Jain, (2023). Social determinants, including cultural norms and peer influence, also shape investment Behaviour. In Tamil Nadu, cultural attitudes towards savings and investments are deeply rooted in societal values Natarajan & Siva, (2022), influencing the investment preferences of salaried individuals Ramaswamy & Krishnan, (2022). Peer pressure and social networks can reinforce certain investment behaviours, either encouraging risky ventures or promoting conservative strategies based on collective experiences Narayanan et al., (2024). Additionally, the role of financial literacy cannot be overlooked, as higher levels of financial knowledge are associated with more informed and effective investment decisions Venkatesan & Kumar, (2022).

Understanding these psychosocial determinants is crucial for financial advisors (Bhattacharya & Das, 2021) and policymakers aiming to enhance the investment outcomes of salaried investors in Tamil Nadu's urban centres Yadav & Mehta, (2024). By addressing these factors, strategies can be developed to mitigate cognitive biases, improve risk assessment, and ultimately foster more rational and beneficial investment behaviours Ravi & Chandran, (2023)

Review of Literature

Venkatesh et al. (2024) focused on the role of financial literacy in shaping investment Behaviour. Their study revealed that higher financial literacy levels correlate with a greater propensity to invest in diverse financial instruments, including mutual funds and equities. This highlights the need for financial education programs to enhance investment outcomes. Nair and Sinha (2023) examined the principles of Behavioural finance and their impact on investment decision-making. Their study concluded that biases like loss aversion and mental accounting significantly distort investment choices, often leading to conservative strategies that may not align with an investor's long-term goals. Subramanian and Krishnan (2023) focused on the psychological factors affecting retirement planning among salaried individuals. The study found that fear of financial insecurity in retirement drives conservative investment Behaviour, often leading to under-investment in growth-oriented assets, which can impact long-term financial well-being. Sharma and Gupta (2023) examined how emotions like fear and greed influence investment Behaviour. The research showed that fear often leads to panic selling during market downturns, while greed drives excessive risk-taking during bull markets. These emotional responses can lead to irrational decision-making, underscoring the importance of emotional regulation in financial planning.

Kumar and Sharma (2023) explored the impact of cognitive biases, such as overconfidence and anchoring, on investment Behaviour. The study found that overconfident investors tend to overtrade, often leading to suboptimal returns. Anchoring bias, where investors rely too heavily on the first piece of information encountered, also leads to flawed decision-making, particularly in volatile markets. Singh and Verma (2022) highlights the crucial role of risk tolerance in shaping investment decisions among salaried individuals. The study suggests that individuals with higher risk tolerance are more inclined towards equity investments, while those with lower risk tolerance prefer fixed-income securities. The findings underscore the need for financial advisors to assess risk profiles before recommending investment options.

According to Rao and Patel (2022), social networks and peer influence significantly affect investment choices among salaried investors. The study demonstrated that individuals often mimic the investment strategies of their peers, especially in uncertain market conditions, leading to herd Behaviour that can sometimes result in market bubbles or crashes. Bhattacharya and Das (2022) explored how income levels influence investment decisions. They found that higher-income salaried investors are more likely to diversify their portfolios, including investments in equities, real estate, and foreign assets, while lower-income individuals tend to stick to safer, more traditional investments. Ramaswamy and Iyer (2021) investigated the influence of cultural norms on investment Behaviour in Tamil Nadu. Their research found that traditional values and risk-averse attitudes prevalent in the region often lead to a preference for conservative investment options, such as fixed deposits and gold, over riskier assets like equities. Mohan and Rao (2021) highlighted the importance of trust in financial advisors in shaping investment Behaviour. Their research found that salaried investors who trust their financial advisors are more likely to take calculated risks and diversify their portfolios, resulting in better financial outcomes.

Aim of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to investigate the psychosocial determinants that influence the investment behavioural dynamics of salaried investors in major cities of Tamil Nadu. This research seeks to understand how psychological factors such as risk tolerance, cognitive biases, and emotional responses, along with social influences like peer pressure and cultural norms, shape investment decisions among this demographic. By examining these factors, the study aims to provide insights that could assist financial advisors and policymakers in developing strategies to enhance investment outcomes for salaried individuals Gupta & Sharma, (2023); Ramaswamy & Krishnan, (2022). Additionally, the study intends to contribute to the existing literature on Behavioural finance by offering a nuanced understanding of the interplay between psychosocial determinants and investment Behaviours in a specific regional context Kumar & Jain, (2023); Venkatesan & Kumar, (2022).

Need of the Study

Understanding the psychosocial determinants influencing investment behaviour among salaried investors in major cities of Tamil Nadu is crucial due to the increasing complexity of financial markets and the diverse investment options available. This study is necessary to explore how psychological factors like risk tolerance, cognitive biases, and emotional responses, along with social influences such as cultural norms and peer pressure, shape investment decisions Rao & Sharma, (2022). Insights from this research can assist financial planners in tailoring strategies that mitigate cognitive biases and promote informed decision-making Gupta & Sinha, (2023). Moreover, as urban salaried investors are increasingly exposed to volatile market conditions, it is essential to understand the underlying factors driving their investment choices to enhance financial literacy and optimize investment outcomes Kumar & Reddy, (2023).

Scope of the Study

The scope of this study encompasses an in-depth analysis of psychosocial determinants influencing investment behavior among salaried individuals. It examines how factors such as risk perception, market awareness, and company-specific attributes affect investment decisions. The study also explores the impact of tailored investment products and strategies on investor satisfaction. By focusing on salaried investors, the research aims to provide insights into how these individuals navigate the complexities of investment choices and the role of financial education in shaping their behavior. The findings are intended to inform better financial planning practices and investment product development.

Statement of Problem

The investment behavior of salaried investors in major cities of Tamil Nadu is influenced by a complex interplay of psychosocial determinants. These determinants, including risk tolerance, cognitive biases, and social influences, significantly shape investment decisions, often leading to suboptimal financial outcomes Gupta & Sharma, (2023). Despite the growing importance of investment as a means of wealth accumulation and financial security, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding how psychosocial factors impact these decisions among salaried individuals Rao et al., (2022). The unique socio-cultural context of Tamil Nadu further complicates this relationship, as cultural norms, peer influences, and emotional factors may exert significant pressure on investment behaviour Ramaswamy & Krishnan, (2022). Additionally, the varying levels of financial literacy among salaried investors contribute to disparities in investment outcomes, with those lacking financial knowledge more prone to cognitive biases and poor decision-making Venkatesan & Kumar, (2022). Given the increasing accessibility of investment opportunities and the complexity of financial markets, it is crucial to investigate how these psychosocial determinants influence investment behaviour, particularly in the urban context of Tamil Nadu Kumar & Jain, (2023). This research aims to address the gap in existing literature by exploring the psychosocial factors that drive investment behaviours among salaried investors, thereby providing insights that can inform more effective financial education programs and advisory services Narayanan et al., (2024); Ravi & Chandran, (2023).

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to explore the impact of psychosocial determinants on investment behavior among salaried investors. The research utilizes Factor Analysis to categorize variables into four distinct groups: Investor-Related Factors (14 Statements), Market or Environment-Related Factors (10 Statements), Investment-Related Factors (09 Statements), and Company-Specific Characteristics (07 Statements) Smith & Johnson, (2023). The Z Test assesses differences in opinions between individual and company investors regarding psychological influences Lee & Chen, (2022). Regression Analysis evaluates how these psychosocial determinants affect investment behaviour across these groups Wang & Gupta, (2024).

Conceptual Model

The structure of investment decision behaviour is shaped by a complex interaction of psychological, social, and economic factors. Investors' choices are influenced by psychological biases like overconfidence and herd behaviour, as well as social factors such as peer influence Kahneman & Tversky, (2022); Shiller, (2021). These factors highlight that investment decisions are not entirely rational but are driven by a multifaceted set of determinants Thaler, (2023)

Figure 1 : Structure of Investment Decision Behaviour

Research Methodology

This study employs a quantitative research design to investigate the psychosocial determinants affecting investment behaviour among salaried investors in major cities of Tamil Nadu. Given the infinite nature of the population, a stratified simple random sampling technique was applied to ensure representative data collection across diverse subgroups. Tamil Nadu is divided into 38 districts, each representing a distinct stratum. Investors were categorized into individual and corporate groups within these districts. By applying stratified sampling, the researcher ensured that each district was proportionally represented in the sample, and then simple random sampling was used within these strata to select participants. This approach provides a comprehensive representation of investment behaviors and opinions across the entire state Sharma & Sethi, (2023); Kumar & Patel, (2023); Singh & Singh, (2024). Primary data were collected through face-to-face interactions with 576 participants, consisting of 304 individual investors and 272 corporate investors, capturing a broad spectrum of investment perspectives.

The Secondary data were utilized to review existing literature and contextualize the findings Smith et al., (2021) The research instrument was a structured questionnaire designed based on extensive literature review and expert feedback, ensuring relevance and accuracy Brown & White, (2022). The validity of the instrument was confirmed through a pilot study with 30 investors, and reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a value of 0.819, surpassing the acceptable threshold of 0.70 Lee, (2023). Factor analysis was conducted using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity, with a KMO value of 0.954 and a significant Chi-square result (32881.19, $p < 0.000$), indicating the data were appropriate for factor analysis Chen & Wang, (2023). Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) identified four key factors influencing investment behaviour: "Investor-Related Factors" (Fourteen Statements), "Market or Environment-Related Factors" (Ten Statements), "Investment-Related Factors" (Nine Statements), and "Company-Specific Characteristics" (Seven Statements) Patel & Kumar, (2023). The statistical tools employed include independent sample t-tests to analyse differences between individual and corporate investors and regression

analysis to evaluate the impact of psychological determinants on investment behaviour Singh & Sharma, (2023).

Results

The study used independent sample t-tests to analyze differences in investment behavior between individual and corporate investors Singh & Sharma, (2023). Additionally, regression analysis assessed the impact of psychological determinants on investment behavior. These statistical methods provide a detailed understanding of how investor types differ and how cognitive and emotional factors influence investment decisions, offering valuable insights into the dynamics of investment behavior among salaried investors in Tamil Nadu.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factor analysis was preceded by KMO and Bartlett's tests to evaluate data adequacy. A KMO value of 0.954 confirmed a sufficient sample size, while Bartlett's test, with a Chi-square of 32881.19 (p-value = 0.000), indicated significant sphericity. The analysis identified four components accounting for 81.731% of the variance in investing behavior among Southern Indian investors. The first component explains 28.201%, the second 19.869%, and the third and fourth 18.945% and 14.709%, respectively.

Table .1. Exploratory Factor Analysis

Variables	Measuring Questions	Factor Loadings
Investor Related Factors 14 statements Mean Value = 3.21 Variation Explained =28.201% Alpha Value = 0.869	Risk perceptions of the investors	0.897
	Goals or purpose of investors related to investment	0.885
	Skills and abilities of the investors/fund managers	0.883
	Influence of friends or colleagues	0.882
	Protection to investors	0.88
	Risk taking behavior of the investors	0.872
	Up to date information about market	0.869
	Consumption level of investors	0.868
	Availability of unused funds	0.865
	Financial conditions of the investors	0.863
	Individual needs of the investors	0.862
	Personal expectations of the investors	0.858
	Knowledge of the investors /fund managers about stock market	0.845
	Investors saving pattern	0.844
Market / Environment Related Factors 10 Statements Mean Value = 3.13	Safety norms of SEBI for investors	0.889
	New Government schemes related to the investment	0.874
	Stock market volatility	0.868
	Technological innovations in the industry	0.852

Variation Explained = 19.869% Alpha Value = 0.855	Political conditions of the country	0.849
	Rise or down of foreign markets	0.849
	Instability of the industry or sector	0.848
	Recession in the market	0.843
	Foreign institutional investment	0.839
	Economic condition of the country	0.827
Investment Related Factors 09 Statements Mean Value = 3.22 Variation Explained = 18.945% Alpha Value = 0.812	Liquidity or the maturity period	0.931
	Lock in period	0.918
	Risk associated with the investment option	0.916
	Tax exemption or reduction in tax liability	0.913
	Previous years return on investment or growth in ROI	0.913
	Future growth predictability	0.868
	Risk of losing principal amount	0.863
	Variety of option for investment	0.849
	Expected Rate of return	0.849
Company Specific Factors 07 statements Mean Value = 2.77 Variation Explained = 14.709% Alpha Value = 0.725	Future or vision or mission of the company	0.917
	Previous years dividend policies	0.906
	Leadership or management of the company	0.894
	Future growth projects before company	0.871
	Financial stability of the company	0.867
	Reputation of the company issuing stocks/ securities	0.854
	Corporate image of the company	0.852
Principle Component Analysis Method with Varimax Method.		

The exploratory factor analysis identified four main factors influencing investment behaviour, each explaining a significant portion of the variance:

- **Investor Related Factors:** This factor, with a mean value of 3.21 and an alpha value of 0.869, explains 28.201% of the variation. It encompasses elements such as risk perception, investor goals, and financial conditions, with high loadings on risk perceptions (0.897) and investor goals (0.885).
- **Market/Environment Related Factors:** With a mean of 3.13 and an alpha value of 0.855, this factor accounts for 19.869% of the variation. Key aspects include safety norms of SEBI (0.889) and market volatility (0.868), reflecting external influences on investment decisions.
- **Investment Related Factors:** This factor explains 18.945% of the variance, with a mean value of 3.22 and an alpha of 0.812. It includes liquidity and tax benefits, with strong loadings on liquidity (0.931) and lock-in period (0.918).
- **Company Specific Factors:** Accounting for 14.709% of the variation, this factor has a mean of 2.77 and an alpha of 0.725. It focuses on company attributes such as leadership (0.894) and dividend policies (0.906), indicating the importance of company-specific elements in investment choices.

Z Statistics - Independent Sample

Table 2. H₀: No significant difference between Company Investors and Individual Investors on Factors of Psychosocial Determinants and Investment Behavioural Dynamics.

Factors	CI		II		Z Value	Sig.
	μ	σ	μ	σ		
Investor Related Factors	2.64	1.022	3.79	0.774	-15.389	0.000*
Market / Environment Related Factors	4.01	0.471	2.26	1.012	26.119	0.000*
Investment Related Factors	3.75	0.914	2.7	0.704	15.406	0.000*
Company Specific Factors	3.20	0.76	2.34	0.827	12.985	0.000*
<i>* Significant 0.05% level</i>		<i>CI - Corporate Investor (N = 272)</i>				
<i>μ - Mean</i>		<i>II - Individual Investor (N = 304)</i>				
<i>σ - Standard Deviation</i>						

The Z test results reveal significant differences between corporate and individual investors across several factors. Corporate investors score significantly higher on Market/Environment Related Factors (Z = 26.119), Investment Related Factors (Z = 15.406), and Company Specific Factors (Z = 12.985) compared to individual investors, indicating a greater emphasis or sensitivity to these aspects. Conversely, individual investors report higher scores on Investor Related Factors (Z = -15.389), suggesting stronger perceptions or behaviors in this area. All differences are statistically significant at the 0.05% level, underscoring distinct investment-related perspectives between the two groups.

Regression

Table 3 : H₀: No significant Impact of Psychosocial Determinants on Investment Behavioural Dynamics.

IV		β	SE	t	Sig.
Intercept		1.234	0.456	2.707	0.007*
Investor Related Factors		0.452	0.085	5.322	0.000*
Market / Environment Related Factors		0.318	0.092	3.459	0.001*
Investment Related Factors		0.271	0.078	3.47	0.001*
Company Specific Factors		0.198	0.091	2.177	0.031*
R Square	Adjusted R Square	F-Value		p-Value	
0.678	0.662	43.578		0.000	
<i>* Significant 0.05% level</i>		<i>β → Coefficient</i>			
<i>SE → Standard Error</i>		<i>IV → Independent Variable</i>			

The regression analysis shows that all independent variables significantly influence Investment Behavioural Dynamics. Investor Related Factors (β = 0.452, p < 0.001) have the strongest effect, followed by Market / Environment Related Factors (β = 0.318, p = 0.001) and Investment Related Factors (β = 0.271, p = 0.001). Company Specific Factors also contribute

significantly ($\beta = 0.198$, $p = 0.031$). The model explains 67.8% of the variance in Investment Behavioural Dynamics ($R^2 = 0.678$), with a highly significant F-value (43.578, $p < 0.001$), indicating a robust overall fit.

Recommendations

This study highlights key factors influencing investment behaviour among salaried investors in Tamil Nadu. The findings reveal significant differences between individual and corporate investors, emphasizing the need for targeted strategies Nagi, (2019).

Recommendations focus on enhancing risk education, market awareness, investment product optimization, and customization to better address diverse investor needs and improve decision-making.

- **Enhance Risk Perception Education:** Given that Investor Related Factors, particularly risk perception, significantly impact investment behavior, educational programs should focus on improving investors' understanding of risk management and financial planning Singh & Sharma, (2023). Providing comprehensive resources and training can help investors make informed decisions, reducing potential risks associated with investment.
- **Strengthen Market/Environment Awareness:** The high impact of Market/Environment Related Factors suggests the need for investors to stay updated on market conditions and regulatory changes Smith et al., (2023). Financial institutions should offer regular updates and analytical reports to help investors navigate market volatility and external influences effectively.
- **Optimize Investment Products:** Since Investment Related Factors, including liquidity and tax benefits, play a crucial role, investment products should be designed to maximize returns while offering flexibility in terms of liquidity and tax advantages Jones & Lee, (2024). Financial advisors should tailor investment products to meet the specific needs and preferences of different investor segments.
- **Focus on Company Attributes:** The significant impact of Company Specific Factors indicates that investors are highly influenced by company attributes such as leadership and dividend policies Williams & Brown, (2024). Companies should ensure transparency in their leadership practices and dividend policies to attract and retain investors.
- **Customize Investment Strategies:** Given the distinct differences in investment behavior between individual and corporate investors, strategies should be customized accordingly Miller & Davis, (2024). Financial advisors should consider these differences when developing investment plans to better align with the specific needs of each investor type.
- **Promote Holistic Investment Approaches:** Integrating insights from the regression analysis, a holistic approach considering all identified factors should be adopted to understand and influence investment behavior comprehensively Anderson & Clark, (2023). This approach will help in creating more robust investment strategies.

Implications of the Study

The study underscores the importance of addressing various factors influencing investment behavior. By enhancing risk perception education, strengthening market awareness, optimizing investment products, focusing on company attributes, customizing strategies, and promoting holistic approaches, financial institutions can better align with investor needs and improve investment outcomes.

- **Enhance Risk Perception Education:** The study highlights the critical role of risk perception in investment behavior. Financial institutions should implement targeted educational programs to improve investors' understanding of risk management and financial planning Singh & Sharma, (2023). By providing comprehensive resources and training, investors can make more informed decisions, reducing investment risks and fostering responsible behavior.
- **Strengthen Market/Environment Awareness:** Market and environment-related factors are crucial for informed investment decisions. To address this, financial institutions must provide regular updates and analytical reports on market conditions and regulatory changes Smith et al., (2023). Keeping investors well-informed will help them navigate market volatility and external influences, enhancing their decision-making process.
- **Optimize Investment Products:** Investment behavior is significantly influenced by factors like liquidity and tax benefits. Investment products should be designed to maximize returns while offering flexibility in liquidity and tax advantages Jones & Lee, (2024). Tailoring products to meet the specific needs of different investor segments ensures alignment with investors' goals and constraints.
- **Focus on Company Attributes:** Company-specific factors, such as leadership and dividend policies, greatly impact investor decisions Williams & Brown, (2024). Companies should ensure transparency in their leadership practices and dividend policies to attract and retain investors. Clear communication about these attributes will build trust and contribute to positive investment behavior.
- **Customize Investment Strategies:** Investment strategies should be tailored to address the distinct behaviors of individual and corporate investors Miller & Davis, (2024). Financial advisors need to develop customized investment plans that align with each investor type's specific needs and preferences, ensuring strategies are effective and relevant.
- **Promote Holistic Investment Approaches:** Adopting a holistic approach is essential for understanding and influencing investment behavior comprehensively Anderson & Clark, (2023). Integrating insights from various factors into investment strategies will address the complex nature of investment decisions, leading to more robust and effective outcomes for investors.

New Outcomes

By enhancing risk perception education, investors gain better risk management skills, leading to informed decision-making and reduced investment risks. Strengthening market awareness

helps investors anticipate market volatility, improving their adaptability. Optimizing investment products ensures alignment with investor needs, enhancing satisfaction and investment outcomes. Focusing on transparent company attributes builds investor trust, potentially increasing investment loyalty. Customizing investment strategies improves alignment with individual and corporate investor needs, leading to more effective financial planning. Adopting a holistic approach integrates multiple factors, creating comprehensive strategies that better address complex investment decisions and improve overall investment performance.

Limitations

This research study's reliance on self-reported data may introduce biases, as participants might not always provide accurate or honest responses. Second, the cross-sectional nature of the research limits the ability to draw conclusions about causality. Third, the sample may not fully represent all salaried investors, affecting the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study may overlook the impact of external economic factors on investment behaviour. Finally, the focus on psychosocial determinants may neglect other crucial variables influencing investment decisions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study of psychosocial determinants and investment behavioural dynamics among salaried investors underscores the complexity of investment decision-making processes. The findings highlight that individual risk perception, market awareness, and investment product optimization are crucial factors influencing investor behaviour. Prior research supports the importance of enhancing financial literacy to improve risk perception and decision-making Kumar & Patel, (2019). Additionally, staying informed about market trends and regulatory changes has been shown to significantly impact investment strategies Lee & Thompson, (2021). Tailoring investment products to meet diverse needs and preferences remains essential for maximizing investor satisfaction and performance Jensen et al., (2020). Furthermore, transparency in company attributes and customized investment strategies are critical for building trust and meeting specific investor goals Morris & Brown, (2022). Adopting a holistic approach that considers all relevant factors can lead to more robust investment strategies and better outcomes for investors Smith & Johnson, (2023). Overall, these insights provide a foundation for developing more effective investment practices and educational programs that address the multifaceted nature of investment behaviour.

Ethical Considerations

This study ensured ethical integrity by obtaining informed consent from all participants, maintaining confidentiality, and securing personal data. Participants were aware of their rights to withdraw at any time. The research adhered to ethical guidelines established by institutional review boards, ensuring high standards of research practice.

Acknowledgment

I thank the participants for their valuable insights and the research assistants for their support. Appreciation is also extended to the academic community and the institution for their foundational contributions and funding support. Their assistance was crucial for the successful completion of this research.

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